

Utilizing programming traces to explore the dimensions of novice programmers' code writing skill

Yingbin Zhang
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
yingbin2@illinois.edu

Luc Paquette
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
lpaq@illinois.edu

Juan D. Pinto
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
jdpinto2@illinois.edu

Aysa Xuemo Fan
University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
xuemof2@illinois.edu

ABSTRACT

Studies have found that novice programmers are weak in code writing. However, it is unclear what subskills code writing is composed of, and which subskills novices are weak in. This study utilizes programming traces to identify latent subskills that constitute code writing so that teachers can offer specific instruction on the weak subskills. Data were collected from an undergraduate course teaching introductory computer science in Java. Six hundred and fourteen students made submissions to homework programming questions in a web-based learning system. We used the submission traces to compute eleven features related to correctness and time students spent on their submissions. To investigate the underlying factors contributing to these features, we conducted an exploratory factor analysis on two-thirds of students selected randomly and identified four factors. The first factor, code style proficiency, was mainly related to checkstyle errors. The second, syntactic proficiency, concerned compiler errors. The third factor, semantic proficiency, concerned runtime errors and logic errors. The fourth factor, syntactic debugging proficiency, concerned the success rate and time required for fixing compiler and checkstyle errors. The confirmatory factor analysis conducted on the remaining one-third of data supported the four-factor structure. We linked these factors to the extant taxonomy and framework of programming skills.

Keywords

Novice programmer, CS1, Code writing, Factor analysis, Programming trace analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Researchers have found most students in introductory computer science (CS1) courses did not know how to program by the end of the course [1, 2]. This finding raised concerns about students' code writing skills. Studies have investigated explanations for the incapacity and found that students were weak at prerequisites of code writing skill, such as code tracing and reading [4-7]. How to enhance student' prerequisites and the writing skill itself have been explored [8, 9].

However, there has been little investigation on the skills that compose novice programmers' code writing proficiency. Such effort is valuable because it enhances our understanding of the code writing process of novice programmers, which in turn could lead to the design of more targeted instruction to address weaknesses in specific skills. This study aims to address this gap by combining

programming trace analysis and factor analysis to explore and model the underlying dimensions of code writing. Specifically, we extracted features related to code writing from undergraduates' programming trace data in a CS1 course and conducted factor analyses to discover the underlying factors accounting for these features. We regarded these factors as code writing skills. This study investigated two research questions. Research question 1: What latent factor model can we identify underlying the features? Research question 2: What code writing skills do the factors represent?

1.1 Novice programming skills

Programming activities require both declarative knowledge and procedural skills [9]. Declarative knowledge in programming may include the basic understanding of programming constructs [10] and programming language syntax [11]. Procedural skills enable individuals to apply their declarative knowledge to solve problems [12]. Studies have identified three distinct but related skills in novice programmers: code tracing, explaining (or reading), and writing [1, 6-8, 13, 14]. Tracing is the skill of compiling and executing a program and forecasting state changes and outputs [8]. Explaining refers to the ability to explain the function or purpose of a program in plain language [6]. Writing is the ability of generating a program to perform a task [13].

Many studies have focused on supporting novice programmers' learning of code writing skills, but it is unclear what constitutes code writing [15]. Can it be decomposed into subskills and what are they? Xie et al. proposed a framework that decomposes reading and writing across the dimensions of semantics and template [9]. Writing semantics is the skill of translating an unambiguous description to code, while writing template is the skill of identifying the objective of an ambiguous problem description and creating a plan that uses a template (reusable abstraction of programming knowledge) to solve the problem. However, the framework was developed from the perspective of instruction and may not align with the structure of code writing produced by novice programmers.

Researchers have used the Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes (SOLO) taxonomy to evaluate responses to problems requiring different programming skills [17, 18]. This taxonomy typically classifies responses to a programming problem into four sequential levels [9]: (1) prestructural responses lack understanding of the problem or show knowledge unrelated to the problem; (2) unistructural responses provide a description for a small part of the code; (3) multistructural responses provide a line-by-line description of most of the code; (4) relational responses summarize the code in terms of its purpose. A general agreement is that solving an unfamiliar problem requires relational responses [19].

1.2 Programming trace analysis

There is an increasing interest in programming trace analysis because it can provide fine-grained information about how problem-solving and learning processes unfold [20, 21] and helps build personalized and adaptive programming learning environments [22].

Y. Zhang, L. Paquette, J. D. Pinto, and A. X. Fan. Utilizing programming traces to explore the dimensions of novice programmers' code writing skill. In B. Akram, T. Price, Y. Shi, P. Brusilovsky, and S. Hsiao, editors, Proceedings of the 6th Educational Data Mining in Computer Science Education (CSEDM) Workshop, pages 50-56, Durham, United Kingdom, July 2022.
© 2022 Copyright is held by the author(s). This work is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license.

For example, Berland et al. presented high school students with a task that required them to program virtual robots to play soccer [20]. The programming environment logged each of the students' change to their programs. Based on programming traces, they investigated how students' program state evolved over time. The results showed that on average, program states experienced three phases: exploration, tinkering, and refinement. Throughout these phases, the quality of programs gradually increased. This study revealed how programming trace analysis could inform us about novice programmers' progress toward the final solution and the role of tinkering in their learning.

Researchers have used programming traces to explore programming behaviors and proficiencies and predict future course performance. A well-known metric based on programming traces is the Error Quotient [23]. This metric characterizes the extent to which a student struggles with syntax errors while solving a programming problem [23]. A student with a high Error Quotient struggles with the problem more than a student with a low Error Quotient. Error Quotient does not consider how students handle the semantic errors of a program [24]. The Normalized Programming State Model (NPSM) addressed this limitation by modeling students' programming activities in terms of the change in both syntactic and semantic correctness [24].

From among these different approaches, the present study is closer to NPSM because it considers both syntactic and semantic correctness. It differentiates from it by focusing on the underlying structure among metrics that characterize programming trajectories, rather than on finding metrics that have the best predictive power on course performance. Our assumption is that these metrics are the manifestation of students' programming proficiencies. Factors that account for the covariances among these metrics may represent programming proficiencies, and different factors represent different subskills. It is critical to disentangle various subskills and identify those where a student is weakest. Such understanding can help to build better learner models and provides insights for personalized intervention. This effort, together with developing accurate prediction models, may move us toward closing the loop of learning analytics [25].

2. METHODS

2.1 Participants and data

Participants were undergraduates in a CS1 course at a public university in the U.S during the Fall 2019 semester. This study only included those who completed the course, finished more than half of homework problems, and approved the use of their data for research purpose. In total, 612 students were included, among which, 30.08% were female, and 81.36% were freshmen.

The course taught basic computing concepts and techniques in Java during a period of 16 weeks. Example topics were variables, loops, objects, and algorithm analysis. Students needed to finish 69 homework problems outside class, one of which was released every weekday. Each problem presented a programming task that required students to write code to solve. The course instructor expected that a programming problem should take no more than 10–15 minutes to complete.

The coursework was hosted on a web-based, problem-driven learning system. Students used the system to submit solutions to homework problems, quizzes, and exams. Students could submit solutions to problems as many times as they wanted until the homework deadline (or before the quizzes and exams ran out of time) to obtain full credit.

After each submission, the system ran tests to check the correctness of the solution and generated automatic feedback about mistakes. First, the learning system tested whether the code structure was correct, i.e., whether the solution had any checkstyle or compiler errors. A checkstyle error occurred when the code did not match the required style enforced for the course (e.g., an operator was not surrounded by whitespace). If checkstyle or compiler errors existed, the system showed feedback about these errors and stopped. If there were neither checkstyle nor compiler errors, the system compiled the solution and used test cases to examine whether the solution fulfilled the problem requirements. For example, given an input, would the solution generate the correct output? If not, the system would return feedback about test errors. Otherwise, the solution was regarded as correct. Test errors were a mix of runtime errors (the system could compile but not run the solution) and logic errors (the system could run the solution, but the solution did not generate the expected output) [26, 27]. The analysis in this study did not distinguish runtime and logic errors because: (1) from the students' perspective, the presentation of the error feedback looked the same (unlike checkstyle and compiler error feedback, runtime and logic error feedback could not indicate the error line) and (2) prior studies have investigated runtime and logic errors together [24, 28], possibly because they are more general than checkstyle and compiler errors and relatively independent of language [29].

The learning system automatically recorded the code, date, correctness, and error feedback of submissions. In total, there were 291,251 submissions. On average, students made 8.68 submissions, 1.31 checkstyle errors, 5.64 syntax errors, and 0.98 test errors on a problem.

2.2 Code writing-related features

We utilized submission traces on homework programming problems to compute code writing-related features for factor analyses. We only used the homework problems because they were closer to real-world programming tasks, where individuals can manage progress at their own pace and use any necessary resources [30]. The error feedback generated by the learning system provided rich information about errors in each submission. We used this error feedback to extract the number and type of errors present in each submission. We further compared consecutive submissions on the same problem to compute features that measured changes in errors, such as the number of syntax errors present in one submission that were not present in the next consecutive submission. These features were then aggregated across submissions on the same problem. We computed twelve problem-level features, described below.

(1 - 3) The number of each type of error: the total number of checkstyle errors, compiler errors, and test errors students made in a problem. The number of errors has previously been used as a negative indicator of learning and proficiency [9, 31, 32].

(4 - 6) The time required for fixing each type of error: the mean time students spent fixing their checkstyle errors, compiler errors, and test errors. The time spent fixing errors may reflect the extent to which students struggled with those errors [33]. For an error persisting multiple sessions, the sum of time on it across sessions was used as the time for fixing it.

(7 - 9) The failure rate for fixing each type of error. Studies have considered consecutive submissions with the same errors as an important indicator of struggling [23, 33]. The failure rate for fixing checkstyle errors was calculated as the proportion of pairs of successive submissions where all checkstyle errors in the first submission also existed in the second submission among all pairs

where the first submission had checkstyle errors. The failure rates for fixing compiler errors and fixing test errors follow the same operation.

(10 - 11) The rate of making new errors. The rate of making new checkstyle errors is the proportion of pairs of consecutive submissions where a checkstyle error did not exist in the first submission but appeared in the second submission. The rate of making new compiler errors follows the same operation. Code changes that cause new errors is known as fix-inducing changes [34]. Fix-inducing changes may be the result of quick attempts to fix errors without a deep understanding of the problem and the current code. Indeed, experienced programmers are less likely to make fix-inducing changes [35, 36]. We did not compute the rate of making new test errors because the learning system only showed one test error at a time. When a test error did not appear in the first submission of a pair but appeared in the second, this could mean that either this was a new error for the student or that the error already existed in the first submission, but the system did not present it to the student. We could not distinguish between the two situations.

(12) The number of uncommented lines of code in the final submission. We assumed that students with good code writing skills would write few unnecessary lines of code while solving a problem.

Problem difficulties varied, and thus, the raw features were not directly comparable across problems. We used the median of a feature on a problem as an approximate of the problem difficulty regarding the feature and deducted the median from the feature to make features more comparable across problems. Features were then aggregated at the student level by computing the mean of each feature over all problems completed by the student. We used the student-level features for subsequent analyses.

2.3 Analyses

We applied factor analyses to code-writing related features to discover the underlying factors accounting for these features. Since the students' code writing skills are expected to develop during the course, it was decided that aggregating homework submissions over the complete duration of the course would be unreasonable. Thus, we conducted factor analysis only in the submission traces after exam two, which contained 105,219 submissions on 24 problems. We randomly selected two-thirds of the students for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) [37]. We implemented EFA with principal factor analysis and promax rotation via the *psych* library in R [38]. We used promax rotation to allow correlations between the factors.

We then conducted confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) on the remaining one-third of students to test the factor model suggested by EFA. We implement CFA via the *lavaan* library in R [39]. For the goodness of fit, we considered CFI (comparative fit index), TLI (Tucker-Lewis index), and RMSEA (root mean square error of approximation). CFI and TLI contrast the specified model with a model fitted terribly and suggest an acceptable model fit with values > 0.90 [40]. RMSEA represents the difference between the specified model and a model fitted reasonably and suggests an acceptable model fit with values < 0.08 [41].

We examined whether the final factor model had acceptable reliability and validity. Composite reliability (CR) evaluates the internal consistency among features [42]. A CR larger than 0.7 is acceptable. Convergent validity assesses the degree that features converge on a factor [42]. Good convergent validity is indicated by factor loadings and average variance extracted (AVE) larger than 0.5 with $p < 0.05$. Discriminant validity evaluates the degree to which the

factors are distinct [43]. If the square root of each factor's AVE is larger than correlations between any factors, factors are discriminant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 RQ1: What latent factor model can we identify underlying the features?

3.1.1 Exploratory factor analysis

We first examined whether the data were suitable for factor analysis using Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test [37]. The Bartlett's test indicated sufficient correlations among the features ($\chi^2 / df = 36.59, p < 0.001$). The overall KMO was 0.65, indicating that a relatively high proportion of variance in the features might be caused by underlying factors, and all single KMO values were greater than 0.55. Overall, these results suggested that EFA was applicable to the data. A parallel analysis suggested four factors, and thus, we conducted EFA with a four-factor solution.

The initial EFA returned a pattern matrix where the loadings of the number of uncommented lines of code on all factors were smaller than 0.30. Further investigation showed that the number of lines was weakly related to the other features (only one correlation greater than 0.30). Thus, this feature was discarded. The second EFA returned a pattern matrix where all features have a loading larger than 0.35 on one of the four factors (Table 1, in bold). Table 1 shows that each factor was strongly loaded by at least two features. We then conducted CFA to test the factor structure.

Table 1. Pattern matrix with four factors

Factor	1	2	3	4
Number of checkstyle errors	.61	.11	.10	-.00
Making new checkstyle errors	.56	.00	.00	.00
Number of compiler errors	.00	.98	.10	.00
Making new compiler errors	.00	.58	.00	.10
Number of test errors	-.15	.59	.16	-.23
Time for solving test errors	.11	.00	.77	.00
The failure rate of fixing test error	-.00	.26	.65	.00
Time for solving checkstyle errors	.00	.00	.12	.36
Time for solving compiler errors	.00	.00	.12	.55
The failure rate of fixing checkstyle errors	.13	.00	-.12	.35
The failure rate of fixing compiler errors	.00	.26	-.18	.62
Proportion variation	.07	.16	.10	.09
Cumulative variation	.07	.23	.33	.43

3.1.2 Confirmatory factor analysis

We began CFA with the four-factor model suggested by Table 1. Each factor was loaded by the features whose loadings on the factor were in bold in Table 1. However, the fit indices indicated a poor fit (see model 2 in Table 2). We modified the model based on the modification index. After three modifications, the model had acceptable fit indices and became interpretable. CFI and TLI reached 0.90. RMSEA was 0.07. All factor loadings were significant ($p < 0.01$; see figure 3). Thus, we took this model as the final model.

Table 3 displays each factor's composite reliabilities, AVE, and the square root of AVE. The composite reliabilities of the first three factors were larger than or close to 0.7, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Their AVEs were larger or equal to 0.5, indicating acceptable convergent validity. The square roots of their AVEs were larger than their correlations with other factors, suggesting good discriminant validity. For the fourth factor, its composite reliability was 0.46, indicating poor internal consistency. Its AVE was 0.22, indicating poor convergent validity. The square root of its AVE was only larger than one of correlations between it and other factors, indicating poor discriminant validity. We evaluated the criterion validity in section 4.3.

Table 2. Fit indices of the four-factor models in CFA

Model	Modification	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
1	-	.84	.77	.11
2	Let the number of test errors load on factor 3	.92	.88	.08
3	Let the number of test errors not load on factor 2 Add an error correlation between the number of test and compiler errors	.79	.69	.13
Final		.93	.90	.07

Table 3. Composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity

Factor	CR	AVE	Discriminant validity			
			1	2	3	4
1. Code style	.65	.50	(.71)			
2. Syntactic	.73	.59	.40	(.77)		
3. Semantic	.78	.56	.07	.48	(.75)	
4. Syntactic debugging	.46	.22	.54	.54	.25	(.47)

3.2 RQ2: What code writing skills do the factors represent?

The first factor in the final model contained the number of checkstyle errors and the rate of making new checkstyle errors. Checkstyle errors occurred when code did not match the desired style, such as putting whitespace between tokens and using the correct number of spaces for indentation. Thus, we labeled the first

factor as code style proficiency. A correct code style usually required students to consider one line at a time because most style requirements was about a few token (e.g., whitespace between tokens). The correct indentation level required students to consider a few lines at a time, but these lines were a small part of the code. Thus, the response reflecting code style proficiency is at the unistructural level of the SOLO taxonomy [17, 18].

The number of compiler errors and the rate of making new compiler errors loaded on the second factor. A compiler error occurred when code was syntactically incorrect. We expect that a student familiar with the Java syntax would make fewer compiler errors. Thus, we labeled the second factor as syntactic proficiency. Some compiler errors were as simple as code style errors, while others were more complex, such as “constructor Parent in class Parent cannot be applied to given types”. Students need to have multiple lines and even most of the code in mind to avoid such errors. Thus, the response to a problem that requires syntactic proficiency may be at the unistructural or multistructural levels of the SOLO taxonomy [17, 18]. Syntactic proficiency may be related to the skill of writing semantic in Xie et al’s framework of novice programming skills [9].

The number of test errors, the time for fixing test errors, and the failure rate for fixing test errors loaded on the third factor. Test errors occurred when code was free of checkstyle and compiler errors but could not run or generate the expected output given certain inputs. It meant that the code was syntactically correct but semantically incorrect, i.e., failing to fulfill the problem requirements. The loadings of three test-error-relevant features suggest that this factor relates to student’s ability to write semantically correct code to solve a problem. Thus, we labeled the third factor semantic proficiency. Writing semantically correct code for a problem required students to identify the problem objective and create an unambiguous plan or pseudo code. Thus, the response that reflects high semantic proficiency is at the relational level of the SOLO taxonomy [17, 18]. Semantic proficiency may be related to the skill of writing templates in Xie et al’s framework [9].

The failure rate for fixing compiler errors, the failure rate for fixing checkstyle errors, the time for fixing compiler errors, and the time for fixing checkstyle errors loaded on the fourth factor. The first two features concerned the accuracy of debugging compiler and checkstyle errors, while the last two features concerned the speed of debugging. The compiler and checkstyle errors were about the syntax and style. Thus, we labeled the fourth factor as syntactic debugging proficiency. Debugging requires students to locate the error cause and repair the error [26]. The compiler message

Figure 1. The final CFA model. Single-headed arrows represent factor loadings, while double-headed arrows represent correlations. Values in the parentheses are standard errors. All coefficients are standardized and significant ($p < 0.01$).

contained the line number of checkstyle and compiler errors. The causes of checkstyle errors and some compiler errors were the error places. It was easy to locate the cause of these errors and repair them. However, the causes of other compiler errors were at different lines of code. Locating the cause of these errors required students to understand multiple lines or even most of code. Thus, the response reflecting high syntactic debugging proficiency may be at the multistructural level of the SOLO taxonomy [17, 18]. Xie et al.'s framework does not explicitly consider debugging skills [9], but novices are generally weak in this skill [26]. How debugging skills develop along other skills is an important gap awaiting further research.

4. OVERALL DISCUSSION

This study utilized programming traces and factor analysis to explore the latent factors of novice programmers' code writing skill. We identified four factors. Three of the four factors had acceptable composite reliability, convergent and discriminant validity. We linked these factors to the SOLO taxonomy [16], a popular framework for evaluating novice programmers' responses in the field of CS education [17, 18]. Code style and syntactic proficiencies may be related to the skill of writing semantic proposed by Xie et al.'s framework of novice programming skills [9], while semantic proficiency may be related to the skill of writing template in the framework. The framework lacks skills explicitly related to debugging, suggesting research opportunities.

The four factors had weak to moderate associations (see Figure 3), indicating that they are relatively distinctive. CS1 instructors may wish to differentiate their instruction based on students' varying levels of proficiency in these skills. For instance, the correlation between syntactic proficiency and syntactic debugging was 0.54, implying that some students might have a good understanding of Java syntax but not know how to debug Java syntactic errors. This is in line with prior research [26] and suggests that CS instructors should explicitly teach novices debugging strategies.

Overall, the results are promising and call for more investigation in programming trace analysis and code writing skills. A valid theory of novice programmers' code writing skill would go a long way toward guiding the instruction of CS1 courses.

4.1 Limitations and next step

The syntactic debugging factor showed poor internal consistency, composite reliability, and discriminative validity. The fit of the four-factor model was acceptable but far from satisfactory. Overall, the final factor model has rooms for improvement. We also plan to examine the construct validity of the code writing skills by investigating their relationships with external variables that indicate coding writing proficiency, such as prior experiences and exam scores.

The current study developed the factor model based on students' programming traces at the end of a course. It would be interesting to test whether the model generalizes to the beginning of the course, to a different student sample, and to a different learning environment.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] McCracken, M., Almstrum, V., Diaz, D., Guzdial, M., Hagan, D., Kolikant, Y. B., Laxer, C., Thomas, L., Utting, I. & Wilusz, T. 2001. A multi-national, multi-institutional study of assessment of programming skills of first-year CS students. *SIGCSE Bulletin*, 33, 4 (2001), 125-180. <http://doi.org/10.1145/572133.572137>
- [2] Utting, I., Tew, A. E., McCracken, M., Thomas, L., Bouvier, D., Frye, R., Paterson, J., Caspersen, M., Kolikant, Y. B., Sorva, J. & Wilusz, T. A fresh look at novice programmers' performance and their teachers' expectations. Association for Computing Machinery, Canterbury, England, United Kingdom, 2013.
- [3] Jöreskog, K. G. How large can a standardized coefficient be. 1999.
- [4] Lopez, M., Whalley, J., Robbins, P. & Lister, R. 2008. Relationships between reading, tracing and writing skills in introductory programming. In *the Fourth international Workshop on Computing Education Research* (Sydney, Australia, 2008). Association for Computing Machinery, 101-112. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1404520.1404531>
- [5] Venables, A., Tan, G. & Lister, R. 2009. A closer look at tracing, explaining and code writing skills in the novice programmer. In *the fifth international workshop on Computing education research workshop* (Berkeley, CA, USA, 2009). Association for Computing Machinery, 117-128. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1584322.1584336>
- [6] Murphy, L., Fitzgerald, S., Lister, R. & McCauley, R. 2012. Ability to 'explain in plain english' linked to proficiency in computer-based programming. In *The ninth annual international conference on International Computing Education Research* (Auckland, New Zealand, 2012). Association for Computing Machinery, 111-118. <http://doi.org/10.1145/2361276.2361299>
- [7] Lister, R., Adams, E. S., Fitzgerald, S., Fone, W., Hamer, J., Lindholm, M., McCartney, R., Moström, J. E., Sanders, K., Seppälä, O., Simon, B. & Thomas, L. 2004. A multi-national study of reading and tracing skills in novice programmers. *SIGCSE Bull.*, 36, 4 (2004), 119-150. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1041624.1041673>
- [8] Nelson, G. L., Xie, B. & Ko, A. J. 2017. Comprehension First: Evaluating a Novel Pedagogy and Tutoring System for Program Tracing in CS1. In *the 2017 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research* (Tacoma, Washington, USA, 2017). Association for Computing Machinery, 2-11. <http://doi.org/10.1145/3105726.3106178>
- [9] Xie, B., Loksa, D., Nelson, G. L., Davidson, M. J., Dong, D., Kwik, H., Tan, A. H., Hwa, L., Li, M. & Ko, A. J. 2019. A theory of instruction for introductory programming skills. *Computer Science Education*, 29, 2-3 (2019-01-01). 2019), 205-253. <http://doi.org/10/ggm3st>
- [10] Tew, A. E. & Guzdial, M. Developing a validated assessment of fundamental CS1 concepts. Association for Computing Machinery, Milwaukee, Wisconsin, USA, 2010.
- [11] Stefik, A. & Siebert, S. 2013. An Empirical Investigation into Programming Language Syntax. *ACM Trans. Comput. Educ.*, 13, 4 (2013), 19. <http://doi.org/10.1145/2534973>
- [12] Davies, S. P. 1993. Models and theories of programming strategy. *International Journal of Man-Machine Studies*, 39, 2 (1993-01-01). 1993), 237-267. <http://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1006/imms.1993.1061>
- [13] Robins, A., Rountree, J. & Rountree, N. 2003. Learning and Teaching Programming: A Review and Discussion.

- Computer Science Education*, 13, 2 (2003-06-01. 2003), 137-172. <http://doi.org/10.1076/csed.13.2.137.14200>
- [14] Clear, T., Whalley, J., Robbins, P., Philpott, A., Eckerdal, A., Laakso, M. & Lister, R. 2011. Report on the final BRACElet workshop : Auckland University of Technology, September 2010. *Journal of Applied Computing and Information Technology*, 15, 1:T1 (2011-01-01. 2011).
- [15] Davidson, M. J. Towards an Understanding of Program Writing as a Cognitive Process: Analysis of Keystroke Logs. Association for Computing Machinery, Virtual Event, USA, 2021.
- [16] Biggs, J. B. & Collis, K. F. *Evaluating the quality of learning: The SOLO taxonomy (Structure of the Observed Learning Outcome)*. Academic Press, Cambridge, MA, 2014.
- [17] Whalley, J. L., Lister, R., Thompson, E., Clear, T., Robbins, P., Kumar, P. K. A. & Prasad, C. 2006. An Australasian study of reading and comprehension skills in novice programmers, using the bloom and SOLO taxonomies. In *the 8th Australasian Conference on Computing Education - Volume 52* (Hobart, Australia, 2006). Australian Computer Society, Inc., 243-252.
- [18] Lister, R., Simon, B., Thompson, E., Whalley, J. L. & Prasad, C. 2006. Not seeing the forest for the trees: novice programmers and the SOLO taxonomy. *SIGCSE Bull.*, 38, 3 (2006), 118-122. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1140123.1140157>
- [19] Lancaster, T., Robins, A. V. & Fincher, S. A. 2019. Assessment and Plagiarism. In A. V. Robins and S. A. Fincher (Eds), 414-444). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [20] Berland, M., Martin, T., Benton, T., Petrick Smith, C. & Davis, D. 2013. Using learning analytics to understand the learning pathways of novice programmers. *J. LEARN. SCI*, 22, 4 (2013-01-01. 2013), 564-599. <http://doi.org/10.1080/10508406.2014.954750>
- [21] Blikstein, P., Worsley, M., Piech, C., Sahami, M., Cooper, S. & Koller, D. 2014. Programming pluralism: Using learning analytics to detect patterns in the learning of computer programming. *J. LEARN. SCI.*, 23, 4 (2014-01-01. 2014), 561-599. <http://doi.org/10/gfz7xk>
- [22] Rivers, K. & Koedinger, K. R. 2017. Data-driven hint generation in vast solution spaces: a self-improving python programming tutor. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*, 27, 1 (2017-01-01. 2017), 37-64. <http://doi.org/10/gg7fkc>
- [23] Jadud, M. C. 2006. Methods and tools for exploring novice compilation behaviour. In the second international workshop on Computing education research (ICER'06) (2006-01-01, 2006). Association for Computing Machinery, 73-84.
- [24] Carter, A. S., Hundhausen, C. D. & Adesope, O. The Normalized Programming State Model: Predicting Student Performance in Computing Courses Based on Programming Behavior. Association for Computing Machinery, Omaha, Nebraska, USA, 2015.
- [25] Wise, A. F., Knight, S. & Ochoa, X. 2021. What makes learning analytics research matter. *Journal of Learning Analytics*, 8, 3 (2021-12-15. 2021), 1-9. <http://doi.org/10.18608/jla.2021.7647>
- [26] McCauley, R., Fitzgerald, S., Lewandowski, G., Murphy, L., Simon, B., Thomas, L. & Zander, C. 2008. Debugging: A review of the literature from an educational perspective. *Computer Science Education*, 18, 2 (2008-06-01. 2008), 67-92. <http://doi.org/10.1080/08993400802114581>
- [27] Hristova, M., Misra, A., Rutter, M. & Mercuri, R. 2003. Identifying and correcting Java programming errors for introductory computer science students. *SIGCSE Bull.*, 35, 1 (2003), 153-156. <http://doi.org/10.1145/792548.611956>
- [28] Fitzgerald, S., Lewandowski, G., McCauley, R., Murphy, L., Simon, B., Thomas, L. & Zander, C. 2008. Debugging: finding, fixing and flailing, a multi-institutional study of novice debuggers. *Computer Science Education*, 18, 2 (2008-06-01. 2008), 93-116. <http://doi.org/10.1080/08993400802114508>
- [29] Pea, R. D. 1986. Language-independent conceptual "Bugs" in novice programming. *J. EDUC. COMPUT. RES.*, 2, 1 (1986), 25-36. <http://doi.org/10.2190/689T-1R2A-X4W4-29J2>
- [30] Lemos, R. S. 1980. Measuring Programming Language Proficiency. *AEDS Journal*, 13, 4 (1980-01-01. 1980), 261-273. <http://doi.org/10/ghtd6m>
- [31] Becker, B. A., Glanville, G., Iwashima, R., McDonnell, C., Goslin, K. & Mooney, C. 2016. Effective compiler error message enhancement for novice programming students. *Computer Science Education*, 26, 2-3 (2016-07-02. 2016), 148-175. <http://doi.org/10.1080/08993408.2016.1225464>
- [32] Berges, M., Striewe, M., Shah, P., Goedicke, M. & Hubwieser, P. 2016. Towards Deriving Programming Competencies from Student Errors. In *2016 International Conference on Learning and Teaching in Computing and Engineering (LaTICE)* (2016), 19-23.
- [33] Watson, C., Li, F. W. B. & Godwin, J. L. 2013. Predicting Performance in an Introductory Programming Course by Logging and Analyzing Student Programming Behavior. In *2013 IEEE 13th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies* (2013-01-01, 2013), 319-323. <http://doi.org/10.1109/ICALT.2013.99>
- [34] Śliwerski, J., Zimmermann, T. & Zeller, A. 2005. When do changes induce fixes? *SIGSOFT Softw. Eng. Notes*, 30, 4 (2005), 1-5. <http://doi.org/10.1145/1082983.1083147>
- [35] Eyolfson, J., Tan, L. & Lam, P. Do time of day and developer experience affect commit bugginess? Association for Computing Machinery, Waikiki, Honolulu, HI, USA, 2011.
- [36] Rahman, F. & Devanbu, P. Ownership, experience and defects: a fine-grained study of authorship. Association for Computing Machinery, Waikiki, Honolulu, HI, USA, 2011.
- [37] Beavers, A. S., Lounsbury, J. W., Richards, J. K., Huck, S. W., Skolits, G. J. & Esquivel, S. L. 2013. Practical considerations for using exploratory factor analysis in educational research. *Practical assessment, research & evaluation*, 18(2013), 6. <http://doi.org/10.7275/qv2q-rk76>
- [38] Revelle, W. psych: *Procedures for Personality and Psychological Research*. Northwestern University, Evanston, Illinois, 2017.
- [39] Rosseel, Y. 2012. Lavaan: an R package for structural equation modeling. *J. STAT SOFTW*, 48, 2 (2012), 1-36.
- [40] Hu, L. T. & Bentler, P. M. 1999. Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6, 1 (1999-01-01. 1999), 1-55. <http://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>

- [41] Browne, M. W. & Cudeck, R. 1992. Alternative Ways of Assessing Model Fit. *SOCIOL. METHOD. RES.*, 21, 2 (1992), 230-258. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0049124192021002005>
- [42] Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B. & Anderson, R. *Multivariate Data Analysis: A Global Perspective*. Prentice Hall, 2009.

- [43] Fornell, C. & Larcker, D. F. 1981. Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *J. MARKETING RES.*, 18, 1 (1981-01-01. 1981), 39-50. <http://doi.org/10.2307/315131>